

Paper 4**FACTORS WHICH INFLUENCE ON-LINE BUYING BEHAVIOR DURING FESTIVE SEASON****V. T. Shailashri, Dr.P.S.Aithal, Dr. Surekha Shenoy**Professor, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangalore 575001.India
shailashrivt@gmail.com**Abstract**

Rising incomes in the hands of a young population, a growing economy, expansion in the availability of products and services and easy availability of credit all has given rise to new consumer segments and a rising acceptability of debt, whether it is mobile phones, credit cards, apparel or organized retail, people clearly seem to be spending more, particularly on discretionary items. The credit facility from business houses has been increasing at a rapid rate. This shows the terrific cut-throat competition in the ever changing market. Consumers in large metros are opting for online retail and e-commerce for most of their purchases, the trend is slowly penetrating in non-metro cities as well.

Festival Sales are a latest fad in India contributing tremendously to the growth of the online sales. All marketing retailers use the festival time to promote their products – either new or stock clearance products at heavy discounts or other offers (freebies, cash backs, buy 1 get 1 etc), The major shopping festival in India comes around the period of the period of October-November when Diwali is celebrated and most of the online e commerce sites provide big ticket offers during this period having created unique names for such shopping events – for example – Big billion days by Flipkart, Great Indian Shopping Festival by Amazon to name some. This study is an attempt to understand consumer buying behavior in India during the festive season.

Keywords: Consumer Buying Behavior, Online Marketing, Festive season, Digitization**1. INTRODUCTION**

Festival Sales are a latest fad in India contributing tremendously to the growth of the online sales. All marketing retailers use the festival time to promote their products – either new or stock clearance products at heavy discounts or other offers (freebies, cash backs, buy 1 get 1 etc), The major shopping festival in India comes around the period of the period of October-November when Diwali is celebrated and most of the online e commerce sites provide big ticket offers during this period having created unique names for such shopping events – for example – Big billion days by Flipkart, Great Indian Shopping Festival by Amazon to name some.[1,2]

2. OBJECTIVES

The study is being carried out to understand the following key parameters apart from other parameters as part of the survey:

1. Various Factors that contribute highly towards festival spends which determine the consumer buying behaviour.
2. Relationship between Income and Spends during festival sales.
3. Relationship between Spends and payment mode.
4. Relationship between day of sale and the expenditure.
5. Frequency of problems faced by consumers during festival sales shopping.
6. Other patterns observed based on the data captured/generated.
 - Advertisement Channels Influence
 - Items Shopped
 - Websites accessed
 - Eagerness of festival sale

3. CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR

Consumer behaviour deals with the study of buying behaviour of consumers. Consumer behaviour helps us understand why and why not an individual purchases goods and services from the market.[3] The study of consumer behaviour explains as to:

- Why and why not a consumer buys a product?
- When a consumer buys a product?
- How a consumer buys a product?

Consumer Behaviour is a branch which deals with the various stages a consumer goes through before purchasing products or services for his end use.[4]

Why do you think an individual buys a product?

- Need
- Social Status
- Gifting Purpose

Why do you think an individual does not buy a product?

- No requirement
- Income/Budget/Financial constraints
- Taste

When do you think consumers purchase products?

- Festive season
- Birthday
- Anniversary
- Marriage or other special occasions

There are in fact several factors which influence buying decision of a consumer ranging from psychological, social, and economic and so on.

The four type of consumer buying behavior are:

- Routine Response/Programmed Behavior □ buying low involvement frequently purchased low cost items; need very little search and decision effort; purchased almost automatically. Examples include soft drinks, snack foods, milk etc.[5]
- Limited Decision Making □ buying product occasionally. When you need to obtain information about unfamiliar brand in a familiar product category, perhaps. Requires a moderate amount of time for information gathering. Examples include Clothes-- know product class but not the brand.[6]
- Extensive Decision Making □ Complex high involvement, unfamiliar, expensive and/or infrequently bought products. High degree of economic/performance/psychological risk. Examples include cars, homes, computers, education. Spend a lot of time seeking information and deciding. Information from the companies MM; friends and relatives, store personnel etc. Go through all six stages of the buying process.[7]
- Impulse buying □ no conscious planning.[8,9]

We can briefly understand from the above that consumer buying is not an easy process to understand and devise marketing strategies. The purpose of this study is to understand the consumers buying behaviour during online festive sales.

4. METHODOLOGY

Primary Data collection with a small sample of 30 respondents. An Online Google form questionnaire has been devised for the same that enlists questions evoking different responses from the consumers. The responses were coded and entered in SPSS to generate different levels of output analysis in the form of tables and charts.

5 Analysis and Interpretation

Factor Analysis

The following 8 factors as shown below in the figure are analysed using factor analysis to understand as to which of the factors have a higher degree of influence on the consumer buying behaviour during festival shopping.

Which of the below factors influences your decision to purchase during a festival sales? *

(Please Tick Only one Rating for each row)

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Heavy discounts i...	<input type="radio"/>				
Additional freebie...	<input type="radio"/>				
Combo discount ...	<input type="radio"/>				
Free Delivery.	<input type="radio"/>				
Free additional W...	<input type="radio"/>				
Exchange Offers.	<input type="radio"/>				
No-Cost-EMI (Inte...	<input type="radio"/>				
Bank Tie-Ups (10...	<input type="radio"/>				

		Heavy Discounts	Freebies	Combo Discount	Free Delivery	Free Addtl Warranty	Exchnng Offers	No Cost EMI	Bank Tie Ups
Correlation	HeavyDiscount s	1.000	-.104	-.033	-.082	-.041	.049	.015	.123
	Freebies	-.104	1.000	.414	.107	.293	.192	.383	.420
	ComboDiscount	-.033	.414	1.000	.330	.660	.308	.187	.258
	FreeDelivery	-.082	.107	.330	1.000	.159	.300	-.040	-.180
	FreeAddtlnWarranty	-.041	.293	.660	.159	1.000	.505	.373	.470
	ExchnngOffers	.049	.192	.308	.300	.505	1.000	.408	.410
	NoCostEMI	.015	.383	.187	-.040	.373	.408	1.000	.636

BankTieUps	.123	.420	.258	-.180	.470	.410	.636	1.000
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Interpretation

- A correlation matrix is simple a rectangular array of numbers which gives the correlation coefficients between a single variable and every other variables in the investigation.
- With respect to Correlation Matrix if any pair of variables has a value less than 0.5, consider dropping one of them from the analysis (by repeating the factor analysis test in SPSS by removing variables whose value is less than 0.5).
- The off-diagonal elements (The values on the left and right side of diagonal in the table below) should all be very small (close to zero) in a good model. The values in the above table conform to the condition as stated.

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
HeavyDiscounts	1.000	.799
Freebies	1.000	.564
ComboDiscount	1.000	.666
FreeDelivery	1.000	.721
FreeAddtnlWarranty	1.000	.673
ExchngeOffers	1.000	.597
NoCostEMI	1.000	.671
BankTieUps	1.000	.815

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Interpretation

- The next item from the output is a table of communalities which shows how much of the variance (i.e. the communality value which should be more than 0.5 to be considered for further analysis. Else these variables are to be removed from further steps factor analysis) in the variables has been accounted for by the extracted factors.
- BankTieUps , HeavyDiscounts and FreeDelivery have the highest variance
- All these are good extraction values since they are more than 0.5 in value

SUGGESTIONS & CONCLUSION

A sample study of 30 respondents geographically scattered in different cities mostly in South India and with 53% respondents in the 20 to 30 Years age bracket, a detailed SPSS analysis revealed that Festival sales is indeed very beneficial for the marketers. Marketers will need to take holistic approach in preparing marketing campaigns for their products to be promoted during a festival sale on the different ecommerce sites. Flipkart and Amazon are their best bets

in deriving profits. No separate marketing strategy is required to target men and women separately as the proportions of the gender shopping during festival sale are the same.

Reference

- [1] Assael Henry (2006). Consumer Behaviour and Marketing Action. (New York : Thomson Learning) Baroota K.D. (2008). Experimental Design in Behavioural Research. (New Delhi : New Age International (P) Limited)
- [2] Gupta S.P. (2007). Statistical Methods. (New Delhi : S. Chand and Sons)
- [3] Hawkins De., Best Roger J. and Caney Kenneth A. (1996). Consumer Behaviour. (New Delhi : Tata Mc Graw Hill Publishing Co. (P) Ltd.)
- [4] Kaur Parminder (1996). Human Resource Development for Rural Development. (New Delhi : Anmol Publication, Ph.D. Thesis Published)
- [5] Kotler Philip (2000). Marketing Management. (New Delhi : Prentice Hall of India (P.) Ltd.) Mc Neal James U. (1992). Kids as Customers (New York : Lexington Books)
- [6] Mc Neal James U. (1999). The Kids Market! Myths and Realities. (New York : Paramount Market Publishing)
- [7] Naomi Klein (2000). No Logo. (Flamingo: Picador Publishers.)
- [8] Saxena Rajan (2002). Marketing Management. (New Delhi : Prentice Hall of India (P) Ltd.)
- [9] Schiffman Leion G. and Leslie Lazar Kanuk (1997). Consumer Behaviour. (New Delhi : Prentice Hall of India (P) Ltd.)